

Non-Clashing Teaching in Graphs: Algorithms, Complexity, and Bounds*

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Abstract

Kirkpatrick et al. [ALT 2019] and Fallat et al. [JMLR 2023] introduced non-clashing teaching and proved that it is the most efficient batch machine teaching model satisfying the collusion-avoidance benchmark established in the seminal work of Goldman and Mathias [COLT 1993]. Recently, (positive) non-clashing teaching was thoroughly studied for balls in graphs, yielding numerous algorithmic and combinatorial results. In particular, Chalopin et al. [COLT 2024] and Ganian et al. [ICLR 2025] gave an almost complete picture of the complexity landscape of the positive variant, showing that it is tractable only for restricted graph classes due to the non-trivial nature of the problem and concept class.

In this work, we consider (positive) non-clashing teaching for closed neighborhoods in graphs. This concept class is not only extensively studied in various related contexts, but it also exhibits broad generality, as any finite binary concept class can be equivalently represented by a set of closed neighborhoods in a graph. In comparison to the works on balls in graphs, we provide improved algorithmic results, notably including FPT algorithms for more general classes of parameters, and we complement these results by deriving stronger lower bounds. Lastly, we obtain combinatorial upper bounds for wider classes of graphs.

1 Introduction

In classic machine learning models such as PAC-learning, a learner must reconstruct a concept C from a concept class \mathcal{C} using a random sample of examples. In contrast, in machine teaching, the examples are selected from the domain by a teacher whose goal is to aid the learner. Specifically, the teacher wants to minimize the number of labeled examples shown to the learner such that the learner can uniquely reconstruct the concept. Machine teaching is a core area in learning theory, with several models proposed in the literature [SM91, GK95, GM96, Bal08, ZLHZ11, GRSZ16, GRSZ17, MCV⁺19]. Moreover, it has many applications in machine learning, such as sample compression [KW07, DFSZ14, MSWY15, CCMW22], inverse reinforcement learning [HLM⁺16, BN19], training data security [MZ15, ZZW18], and human-robot interaction [TC09, ACYT12].

In this work, we focus on the *non-clashing teaching model* [KSZ19, FKS⁺23], a batch teaching framework where the teacher presents a set of examples to the learner simultaneously. This model has gained significant attention in recent years, since it was shown [KSZ19, FKS⁺23] to require the fewest examples among batch teaching models that adhere to the Goldman-Mathias collusion-avoidance criterion [GM96], a fundamental principle that prevents teacher-learner collusion (e.g., through encoding).

In *non-clashing teaching*, given a finite binary concept class \mathcal{C} , a teacher maps each concept $C \in \mathcal{C}$ to a labeled set of examples $T(C)$ that is consistent with C and called the teaching set of C . The teaching map T must satisfy the non-clashing condition: for each pair of distinct concepts $C, C' \in \mathcal{C}$, at least one of the examples in $T(C) \cup T(C')$ must be

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consistent with exactly one of the two concepts C and C' . If T satisfies this condition and $\max_{C \in \mathcal{C}} |T(C)| = k$, then T is a *non-clashing teaching map* (NCTM) of size k for \mathcal{C} . Notably, the teacher needs to present at most k examples (specifically, $T(C)$) for the learner to uniquely reconstruct any concept $C \in \mathcal{C}$. The non-clashing teaching dimension of \mathcal{C} , denoted by $\text{NCTD}(\mathcal{C})$, is the smallest size of an NCTM for \mathcal{C} .

Machine teaching is often studied in the setting where the teacher is restricted to presenting only positively-labeled examples. Research in this setting dates back to 1980 [Ang80b, Ang80a] and has applications in, e.g., recommendation systems [SPK00], grammatical inference [SO94, Den01], and bioinformatics [WDMH06, YJSS08]. Notably, when $T(C)$ may only consist of positively-labeled examples for all $C \in \mathcal{C}$, the corresponding *positive non-clashing teaching dimension* of \mathcal{C} , denoted by $\text{NCTD}^+(\mathcal{C})$, has been extensively studied [KSZ19, FKS⁺23, CCMR24, GKMR25].

The initial works [KSZ19, FKS⁺23] on non-clashing teaching studied the relationship between the NCTD and the *VC-dimension* (VCD), due to its value in learning theory. A key open question of theirs is whether there is a concept class \mathcal{C} such that $\text{NCTD}(\mathcal{C}) > \text{VCD}(\mathcal{C})$. It was also shown that deciding whether $\text{NCTD}^+(\mathcal{C}) \leq 1$ ($\text{NCTD}(\mathcal{C}) \leq 1$, resp.) is NP-complete when \mathcal{C} is a set of open neighborhoods in a graph G [KSZ19]. Although unstated, by those results, unless the Exponential Time Hypothesis (ETH)¹ fails, there is no algorithm running in $2^{o(f(k) \cdot \sqrt{|V(G)|})}$ time for either problem for any computable function f of the solution size k .²

Any finite binary concept class can be equivalently represented by a set of balls in a graph G (see Fig. 1), where the ball of radius $r \in \mathbb{N}$ centered at the vertex $v \in V(G)$ is the set $B_r(v) := \{u \mid \text{dist}(u, v) \leq r, u \in V(G)\}$ [CCM⁺23]. This was one of two main motivations for the recent works [CCMR24, GKMR25] on *non-clashing teaching* for balls in graphs. The other was that this is a natural and fundamental concept class that has been investigated for related topics like sample compression [CCM⁺23], and its VC-dimension is well-studied [CEV07, BT15, DHV20].

Given a graph G , a set of balls \mathcal{B} in G , and $k \in \mathbb{N}$, NON-CLASH asks whether $\text{NCTD}^+(\mathcal{B}) \leq k$. If \mathcal{B} contains every ball in G , then this problem is known as STRICT NON-CLASH.³ When G is restricted to the class of split or (co-)bipartite graphs, STRICT NON-CLASH remains NP-hard [CCMR24], even if $k = 2$ for the former [GKMR25]. STRICT NON-CLASH can be solved in $2^{2^{\mathcal{O}(\text{vc}(G))}} \cdot |V(G)|^{\mathcal{O}(1)}$ time, where $\text{vc}(G)$ is the vertex cover number of G , and this is tight under the ETH [CCMR24]. This FPT⁴ algorithm was improved upon by considering a more general parameter and problem, as it was shown that NON-CLASH is FPT parameterized by the vertex integrity of G [GKMR25]. As NON-CLASH is W[1]-hard⁵ parameterized by the feedback vertex number, pathwidth, and solution size k combined [GKMR25], these results give a nearly complete picture of its complexity landscape. There is a $2^{\mathcal{O}(|V(G)| \cdot d \cdot k \cdot \log |V(G)|)}$ -time algorithm for NON-CLASH, and unless the ETH fails, there is no $2^{o(|V(G)| \cdot d \cdot k)}$ -time algorithm, even for STRICT NON-CLASH, where d is the diameter of G [GKMR25]. Finally, (near-)optimal NCTMs are known for balls if G is a tree, cycle, cactus or interval graph [CCMR24].

1.1 Our Contributions

We explore non-clashing teaching for balls in graphs from a combinatorial and computational perspective, providing a comprehensive understanding of the problem. As discussed above, the problem is inherently algorithmically intractable. With the goal of obtaining improved algorithmic results for larger graph classes under more general parameters, we study both variants of non-clashing teaching for closed neighborhoods (balls of radius 1) in graphs:

N-NCTD

Input: A graph G , a set \mathcal{B} of closed neighborhoods in G , and a positive integer k .

Question: Is $\text{NCTD}(\mathcal{B}) \leq k$?

N-NCTD⁺

Input: A graph G , a set \mathcal{B} of closed neighborhoods in G , and a positive integer k .

Question: Is $\text{NCTD}^+(\mathcal{B}) \leq k$?

¹Roughly, the ETH states that n -variable and m -clause 3-SAT cannot be solved in $2^{o(n+m)}$ time.

²Their results are proven by reductions from a matching problem in graphs, and they prove that problem is NP-hard by a reduction from n -variable and m -clause 3-SAT that produces a graph with $\Theta(n \cdot m)$ vertices.

³For clarity, we name the problems as in [GKMR25], but note that they are for the positive variant.

⁴A problem with input size n is fixed-parameter tractable (FPT) parameterized by parameter $p \in \mathbb{N}$ if it admits an $f(p) \cdot n^{\mathcal{O}(1)}$ -time algorithm (i.e., an FPT algorithm) for some computable function f .

⁵A problem that is W[1]-hard parameterized by p is not FPT parameterized by p unless $W[1] = \text{FPT}$.

We emphasize that this is as general as studying finite binary concept classes. In fact, the aforementioned representation of any finite binary concept class $\mathcal{C} \subseteq 2^V$ by a set of balls in a graph G , holds for a set of closed neighborhoods in G . Indeed, $V(G) = V \cup \{x_C \mid C \in \mathcal{C}\}$, the x_C vertices form a clique, x_C is adjacent to $v \in V$ if and only if $v \in C$, and $\mathcal{B} = \{N[x_C] \mid C \in \mathcal{C}\}$. See Fig. 1. It is also motivated by the many works that have considered the *VC-dimension* of *closed neighborhoods* in graphs [HW87, ABC95, KKR⁺97, BLL⁺15, DHV20, Duc21, CCM⁺23, CCDV24]. See [FGMT25] for a list of references on other well-studied graph-based concept classes.

Figure 1: Graph G for a binary concept class $\mathcal{C} = \{\{1, 4\}, \{2, 5\}, \{2, 3, 5\}\}$ and $\mathcal{B} = \{N[C]\}_{C \in \mathcal{C}}$.

In Section 2, we present improved algorithmic upper and lower bounds, which match in the case of N-NCTD⁺, unlike in the case of NON-CLASH. Specifically, no algorithmic lower bound was previously known for the NCTD of balls in graphs, however, we prove that, unless the ETH fails, there is no $2^{o(f(k) \cdot |V(G)|)}$ -time algorithm for any computable function f (Theorem 2). This also dramatically improves upon the only previously known lower bound for the NCTD of a concept class, which is that, unless the ETH fails, no $2^{o(f(k) \cdot \sqrt{|V(G)|})}$ -time algorithm exists [KSZ19]. Further, our lower bound is almost tight due to the $2^{\mathcal{O}(k \cdot |V(G)| \cdot \log |V(G)|)}$ -time algorithm that can be inferred from [GKMR25]. We then show that N-NCTD⁺ can be solved in $2^{\mathcal{O}(|E(G)|)}$ time (Theorem 4), and unless the ETH fails, this is tight, i.e., there is no $2^{o(|E(G)|)}$ -time algorithm (Theorem 3); in fact there is even no $2^{o(f(k) \cdot (|V(G)| + |E(G)|))}$ -time algorithm for any computable function f . This is also a new strong lower bound for NON-CLASH.

In Section 3, we provide two highly non-trivial algorithms to prove that N-NCTD⁺ is FPT parameterized by the *treedepth* of G (Theorem 5) and N-NCTD is FPT parameterized by the *vertex cover number* of G (Theorem 7). These are two well-established structural graph parameters that have been considered in, e.g., Bayesian network learning [KP15, HK23] and other areas of AI [GPSS20, EGHK23]. Notably, we again achieve positive results that were not obtained in the setting of balls in graphs as *treedepth* is a more general parameter than *vertex integrity*,⁶ and no FPT algorithm parameterized by a structural graph parameter was known for any concept class when the teacher may use negatively-labeled examples.

Finally, in Section 4, we obtain combinatorial bounds for larger graph classes than those in [CCMR24]. Exploiting forbidden minors, we prove that, if \mathcal{B} is a set of closed neighborhoods in a planar graph G , then $\text{NCTD}^+(\mathcal{B}) \leq 7$ (Theorem 12) and $\text{NCTD}(\mathcal{B}) \leq 5$ (Theorem 13). Employing geometric arguments, we prove that, if \mathcal{B} is a set of closed neighborhoods in a unit square graph G , then $\text{NCTD}^+(\mathcal{B}) \leq 4$ (Theorem 14). See Table 1 for a summary of our results and the literature.

2 Improved Algorithmic Upper and Lower Bounds

In this section, we first prove an algorithmic lower bound for N-NCTD that is stronger than the previous one from the literature, and then tight algorithmic bounds for N-NCTD⁺. We begin by introducing problem-specific terminology. Let G be a graph, \mathcal{B} a set of closed neighborhoods in G , and T a teaching map for \mathcal{B} . If, for all $B \in \mathcal{B}$, $T(B) \subseteq B$, then T is a *positive teaching map* for \mathcal{B} . In either case, T is *non-clashing* for \mathcal{B} if, for all distinct $N[u], N[v] \in \mathcal{B}$, there exists $w \in T(N[u]) \cup T(N[v])$ such that $w \in N[u] \cup N[v]$ and $w \notin N[u] \cap N[v]$; we say that w *distinguishes* $N[u]$ and $N[v]$. For all $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, we set $[n] := \{1, \dots, n\}$.

From the exact exponential algorithm for NON-CLASH in [GKMR25], it can be observed that N-NCTD can be solved in $2^{\mathcal{O}(k \cdot |V(G)| \cdot \log |V(G)|)}$ time. In the next theorem, we provide an improved lower bound, via a reduction from 3-SAT, that almost matches this upper bound. However, we first need the following lemma, which will be useful for the proof of that theorem. Note that, given a graph G , two distinct vertices $u, v \in V(G)$ are *false twins* if and only if $N(u) = N(v)$.

⁶For any problem on a graph G , if it admits an FPT algorithm parameterized by the treedepth of G , then it admits an FPT algorithm parameterized by the vertex integrity of G , but not the other way round.

Table 1: Summary of our results and the literature. NP-h, CN, V , E , [1], and [2] denote NP-hard, closed neighborhoods, $V(G)$, $E(G)$, [GKMR25], and [CCMR24], respectively.

	NCTD ⁺ Balls	NCTD ⁺ CN	NCTD Balls	NCTD CN
Solution size k	NP-h if $k=1$ (Th. 3)	NP-h if $k=1$ (Th. 3)	NP-h if $k=1$ (Th. 2)	NP-h if $k=1$ (Th. 2)
Vertex cover	FPT [1]	FPT (Th. 5)	?	FPT (Th. 7)
Vertex integrity	FPT [1]	FPT (Th. 5)	?	?
Treedepth	?	FPT (Th. 5)	?	?
Treewidth	W[1]-hard [1]	?	?	?
Alg. up. bound	$2^{\mathcal{O}(k \cdot d \cdot V \cdot \log V)}$ [1]	$2^{\mathcal{O}(E)}$ (Th. 4)	$2^{\mathcal{O}(k \cdot d \cdot V \cdot \log V)}$ [1]	$2^{\mathcal{O}(k \cdot V \cdot \log V)}$ [1]
Alg. low. bound	$2^{o(k \cdot d \cdot V)}$ [1]	$2^{o(f(k) \cdot (V + E))}$ (Th. 3)	$2^{o(f(k) \cdot V)}$ (Th. 2)	$2^{o(f(k) \cdot V)}$ (Th. 2)
Planar	Unbounded by cycle [2]	≤ 7 (Th. 12)	≤ 615 [2]	≤ 5 (Th. 13)
Unit square	Unbounded by cycle [2]	≤ 4 (Th. 14)	≤ 615 [2]	≤ 4 (Th. 14)

Lemma 1. *Let G be a graph with 4 pairwise false twins u_1, \dots, u_4 with $N[u_1], \dots, N[u_4] \in \mathcal{B}$. Then, for any NCTM T of size 1 for \mathcal{B} , there exists $i \in [4]$ such that $T(N[u_i]) = \{u_i\}$.*

Proof. If no NCTM of size 1 for \mathcal{B} exists, then the statement trivially holds. So, let T be an NCTM of size 1 for \mathcal{B} . When only considering $N[u_1], \dots, N[u_4]$ from \mathcal{B} , for any $i \in [4]$ and $v \in T(N[u_i])$,

- if $v = u_i$, then v only distinguishes $N[u_i]$ and $N[u_j]$ for all $j \in [4] \setminus \{i\}$;
- if $v = u_j$ for some $j \in [4] \setminus \{i\}$, then v only distinguishes $N[u_i]$ and $N[u_j]$;
- if $v \notin \{u_1, \dots, u_4\}$, then v does not distinguish $N[u_i]$ and $N[u_j]$ for any $j \in [4] \setminus \{i\}$.

Toward a contradiction, suppose that $T(N[u_i]) \neq \{u_i\}$ for all $i \in [4]$. By the above analysis, for all $i \in [4]$, the sole vertex in $T(N[u_i])$ distinguishes $N[u_i]$ and at most one other closed neighborhood in $\{N[u_1], \dots, N[u_4]\} \setminus \{N[u_i]\}$. As there are $4(3)/2 = 6$ such pairs that need to be distinguished, T does not satisfy the non-clashing condition for some pair in $\{N[u_1], \dots, N[u_4]\}$, a contradiction. Thus, there exists $i \in [4]$ such that $T(N[u_i]) = \{u_i\}$. \square

Theorem 2. *Unless the ETH fails, N-NCTD cannot be solved in $2^{o(f(k) \cdot |V(G)|)}$ time for any computable function f .*

Proof. Given an instance φ of n -variable and m -clause 3-SAT, we construct a graph G as follows:

1. for each variable x_i and clause C_j in ϕ , there is a clause vertex c_j , a variable vertex v_i , and two literal vertices t_i and f_i that are both adjacent to v_i ;
2. there is an additional dummy variable vertex v_0 that has no adjacent literal vertices;
3. for all $i \in \{0\} \cup [n]$, there is a set of vertices $\mathcal{V}_i = \{v_i^0, v_i^1, v_i^2, v_i^3, v_i^4\}$ and a special vertex v_i^* , where v_i^* is adjacent to each vertex in \mathcal{V}_i , and each vertex in $\mathcal{V}_i \cup \{v_i^*\}$ is adjacent to v_i ;
4. for all $i \in [n]$, if the literal x_i (\bar{x}_i , resp.) is in the clause C_j in ϕ , then the literal vertex f_i (t_i , resp.) is adjacent to the clause vertex c_j and there is a vertex $c_{j,i}$ adjacent to v_i , c_j , v_i^* , and each vertex in \mathcal{V}_i ;
5. the set $\{c_j\}_{j \in [m]} \cup \{v_i\}_{i \in \{0\} \cup [n]}$ forms a clique.

This concludes the construction of G (see Fig. 2). We set \mathcal{B} to contain the closed neighborhood of each vertex in $\bigcup_{j \in [m]} \{c_j\}$ and $\bigcup_{i \in \{0\} \cup [n]} (\{v_i, v_i^*\} \cup \{v_i^p\}_{p \in [4]})$ (note that, for all $i \in \{0\} \cup [n]$, $N[v_i^0] \notin \mathcal{B}$). Thus, from φ , the reduction outputs the N-NCTD instance $(G, \mathcal{B}, 1)$.

To show the correctness of the reduction in the first direction, let T be an NCTM of size 1 for \mathcal{B} . By Lemma 1, for all $i \in \{0\} \cup [n]$, there exists $p \in [4]$ such that $T(N[v_i^p]) = \{v_i^p\}$, say, w.l.o.g., $T(N[v_i^0]) = \{v_i^1\}$. Hence, for all

Step 1: by Lemma 1, $\forall i \in \{0\} \cup [n]$, $T(N[v_i^p]) = \{v_i^p\}$ for some $p \in [4]$

Step 2: by Step 1, $\forall i \in \{0\} \cup [n]$, $T(N[v_i^*]) \subset \mathcal{V}_i$

Step 3: by Step 2, $T(N[v_0])$ is a clause or variable vertex

Step 4: by Steps 2 and 3, $\forall i \in [n]$, $T(N[v_i]) \subset \{t_i, f_i\}$

Step 5: by Step 4, $\forall j \in [m]$, if $c_j = (x \vee x' \vee x'')$,
then $T(N[c_j]) \subset \{c_{j,x}, c_{j,x'}, c_{j,x''}\}$
(however, some exceptions are possible)

Figure 2: Example of the graph G constructed in the proof of Theorem 2 with $\varphi = (\overline{x_1} \vee x_2 \vee \overline{x_3}) \wedge (\overline{x_2} \vee x_3 \vee x_4)$ in the 3-SAT instance. The two bold rectangles together form a clique. The edges going from vertices in one of the two large dashed rectangles to vertices in the other are omitted for legibility. Only the closed neighborhoods of filled vertices are in \mathcal{B} .

$i \in \{0\} \cup [n]$, $T(N[v_i^*]) \subset \mathcal{V}_i$ since $N[v_i^*] \subset N[v_i^*]$. Therefore, for all $i \in \{0\} \cup [n]$, $T(N[v_i]) \subset (N[v_i] \setminus N[v_i^*])$ since $N[v_i^*] \subset N[v_i]$. As $T(N[v_0])$ is not adjacent to any literal vertices, then it must consist of a clause or variable vertex. As the clause and variable vertices form a clique, for all $i \in [n]$, $T(N[v_i])$ cannot consist of a clause or variable vertex, and hence, $T(N[v_i]) \subset \{t_i, f_i\}$. We extract a variable assignment $\tau: \{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \rightarrow \{\text{True}, \text{False}\}$ as follows: if $T(N[v_i]) = \{t_i\}$, then $\tau(x_i) := \text{True}$, and otherwise, $\tau(x_i) := \text{False}$.

Toward a contradiction, suppose that τ is not a satisfying assignment for φ . Then, there exists a clause C_j in φ that is not satisfied by τ . Let x, x' , and x'' be the 3 variables in C_j in φ (and the corresponding variable vertices in G). By the construction of G and the definition of τ , as C_j is not satisfied, $T(N[x]), T(N[x']), T(N[x'']) \subset N[c_j]$. Thus, as T is non-clashing for $N[c_j]$ and each of $N[x], N[x']$, and $N[x'']$, then $T(N[c_j])$ consists of a vertex $u \in V(G)$, where either (1) $u \in N[c_j]$, $u \notin N[x]$, $u \notin N[x']$, and $u \notin N[x'']$, or (2) $u \notin N[c_j]$, $u \in N[x]$, $u \in N[x']$, and $u \in N[x'']$. No such vertex u exists, contradicting that T is an NCTM for \mathcal{B} . So, τ is a satisfying assignment for φ .

For the reverse direction, let $\tau: \{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \rightarrow \{\text{True}, \text{False}\}$ be a satisfying assignment of the given 3-SAT formula φ . We define a teaching map T for \mathcal{B} as follows. For all $i \in [n]$, if $\tau(x_i) = \text{True}$, then $T(N[v_i]) := \{t_i\}$, and otherwise, $T(N[v_i]) := \{f_i\}$. For all $i \in \{0\} \cup [n]$ and $p \in [4]$, $T(N[v_i^p]) := \{v_i^p\}$. For all $i \in \{0\} \cup [n]$, $T(N[v_i^*]) = \{v_i^0\}$. For all $j \in [m]$, there exists $i \in [n]$ such that $\tau(x_i)$ satisfies C_j , and we set $T(N[c_j]) := \{c_{j,i}\}$. Finally, $T(N[v_0]) := \{v_1\}$.

We prove that T is an NCTM for \mathcal{B} . For all $i \in \{0\} \cup [n]$ and $p \in [4]$, $T(N[v_i^p]) = \{v_i^p\}$ distinguishes $N[v_i^p]$ and $N[w]$ for all $w \in V(G)$ such that $N[w] \in \mathcal{B} \setminus \{N[v_i], N[v_i^*]\}$. For all $i \in \{0\} \cup [n]$ and $p \in [4]$, $T(N[v_i])$ distinguishes $N[v_i]$ and $N[v_i^p]$, as well as $N[v_i]$ and $N[v_i^*]$, as $T(N[v_i]) \subset N[v_i]$, $T(N[v_i]) \cap N[v_i^p] = \emptyset$, and $T(N[v_i]) \cap N[v_i^*] = \emptyset$. For all $i \in \{0\} \cup [n]$ and $p \in [4]$, $T(N[v_i^*])$ distinguishes $N[v_i^*]$ and $N[v_i^p]$ since $T(N[v_i^*]) \subset N[v_i^*]$ and $T(N[v_i^*]) \cap N[v_i^p] = \emptyset$. Thus, all pairs of closed neighborhoods containing $N[v_i^p]$ for some $i \in \{0\} \cup [n]$ and $p \in [4]$ are distinguished. For all $i \in \{0\} \cup [n]$, $N[v_i^*]$ and any other closed neighborhood in \mathcal{B} are distinguished since $T(N[v_i^*]) \subset N[v_i^*]$, but $T(N[v_i^*])$ is not a subset of any closed neighborhood in \mathcal{B} not already covered above.

For all distinct $i \in [n]$ and $q \in \{0\} \cup [n]$, $T(N[v_i]) \subset N[v_i]$ and $T(N[v_i]) \cap N[v_q] = \emptyset$, and so, $N[v_i]$ and $N[v_q]$ are distinguished. For all distinct $j, \ell \in [m]$, $T(N[c_j]) \subset N[c_j]$ and $T(N[c_j]) \cap N[c_\ell] = \emptyset$, and so, $N[c_j]$ and $N[c_\ell]$ are distinguished. For all $i \in [n]$ and $j \in [m]$ such that $c_{j,i} \in T(N[c_j])$, $\tau(x_i)$ satisfies the clause C_j in φ , and so, $T(N[v_i]) \cap N[c_j] = \emptyset$, resulting in $N[v_i]$ and $N[c_j]$ being distinguished by $T(N[v_i])$. For all $i \in [n]$ and $j \in [m]$ such that $c_{j,i} \notin T(N[c_j])$, $N[v_i]$ and $N[c_j]$ are distinguished by $T(N[c_j])$. Lastly, for all $j \in [m]$, $T(N[c_j])$ distinguishes $N[c_j]$ and $N[v_0]$, completing the case analysis. Thus, T is an NCTM for \mathcal{B} .

Finally, if N-NCTD can be solved in $2^{o(f(k) \cdot |V(G)|)}$ time for a computable function f , then 3-SAT can be solved in $2^{o(n+m)}$ time as $f(k) = \mathcal{O}(1)$ and $|V(G)| = \mathcal{O}(n+m)$, contradicting the ETH. \square

A similar reduction proves the following lower bound, which we then prove is tight under the ETH.

Theorem 3. *Unless the ETH fails, N-NCTD⁺ cannot be solved in $2^{o(f(k) \cdot (|V(G)| + |E(G)|))}$ time for any computable function f .*

Proof. Given an instance φ of n -variable and m -clause 3-SAT, we construct a graph G as follows:

1. for each clause C_j in ϕ , there is a clause vertex c_j adjacent to a pendent vertex c'_j ;
2. for each variable x_i in ϕ , there is a variable vertex v_i adjacent to a vertex v'_i as well as 2 literal vertices t_i and f_i ;
3. for all $i \in [n]$, if the literal x_i (\bar{x}_i , resp.) is contained in the clause $C_j \in \phi$, then the literal vertex f_i (t_i , resp.) is adjacent to the clause vertex c_j ;
4. for all $i \in [n]$ and $j \in [m]$ such that c_j is adjacent to t_i or f_i , there is a vertex $c_{j,i}$ adjacent to v_i , v'_i , and c_j .

This concludes the construction of G (see Fig. 3). We set \mathcal{B} to contain the closed neighborhood of each variable vertex v_i , each clause vertex c_j , and each of their pendent vertices v'_i and c'_j . So, from φ , the reduction outputs the N-NCTD⁺ instance $(G, \mathcal{B}, 1)$. We now prove the reduction is correct.

Let T be a positive NCTM of size 1 for \mathcal{B} . For all $i \in [n]$, $T(N[v_i]) \subset \{t_i, f_i\}$ as $N[v'_i] \subset N[v_i]$ and $N[v_i] \setminus N[v'_i] = \{t_i, f_i\}$. We extract a variable assignment $\tau: \{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \rightarrow \{\text{True}, \text{False}\}$ as follows: if $T(N[v_i]) = \{t_i\}$, then $\tau(x_i) = \text{True}$, and otherwise, $\tau(x_i) = \text{False}$.

Figure 3: Example of the graph G constructed in the proof of Theorem 3 with $\varphi = (\overline{x_1} \vee \overline{x_2} \vee \overline{x_4}) \wedge (x_1 \vee \overline{x_2} \vee x_3)$ in the 3-SAT instance. Only the closed neighborhoods of filled vertices are in \mathcal{B} .

Toward a contradiction, suppose that τ is not a satisfying assignment for φ . Then, there exists a clause C_j in φ that is not satisfied by τ . Let x, x' , and x'' be the 3 variables in C_j in φ (and the 3 corresponding variable vertices in G). Since C_j is not satisfied, $T(N[x]), T(N[x']), T(N[x'']) \subset N[c_j]$ by the construction of G and the definition of τ . Thus, as T is non-clashing for $N[c_j]$ and each of $N[x], N[x']$, and $N[x'']$, then $T(N[c_j])$ must consist of a vertex $u \in V(G)$ such that $u \in N[c_j], u \notin N[x], u \notin N[x']$, and $u \notin N[x'']$. It is easy to check that the only possibilities for such a vertex u are c_j and c'_j . However, $T(N[c_j]) \not\subset \{c_j, c'_j\}$ since $N[c'_j] = \{c_j, c'_j\} \subset N[c_j]$, as otherwise T does not satisfy the non-clashing condition for $N[c_j]$ and $N[c'_j]$. Hence, this contradicts that T is an NCTM for \mathcal{B} . Therefore, τ is a satisfying assignment for φ .

For the reverse direction, let $\tau: \{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \rightarrow \{\text{True}, \text{False}\}$ be a satisfying assignment of the 3-SAT formula φ . We define a positive teaching map T for \mathcal{B} . For all $i \in [n]$, if $\tau(x_i) = \text{True}$, then $T(N[v_i]) := \{t_i\}$, and otherwise, $T(N[v_i]) := \{f_i\}$. For all $i \in [n]$, $T(N[v'_i]) := \{v'_i\}$. For all $j \in [m]$, there exists $i \in [n]$ such that $\tau(x_i)$ satisfies C_j , and we set $T(N[c_j]) := \{c_{j,i}\}$. Lastly, for all $j \in [m]$, $T(N[c'_j]) := \{c'_j\}$. We now prove that T is a positive NCTM for \mathcal{B} .

For all $i \in [n]$, $T(N[v_i]) \cap N[v'_i] = \emptyset$, and thus, $T(N[v_i])$ distinguishes $N[v_i]$ and $N[v'_i]$. Moreover, for all $i \in [n]$, $T(N[v'_i]) = v'_i$ distinguishes $N[v'_i]$ and all the other remaining closed neighborhoods in \mathcal{B} . For distinct $i, \ell \in [n]$, $T(N[v_i])$ distinguishes $N[v_i]$ and $N[v_\ell]$ since $T(N[v_i]) \cap N[v_\ell] = \emptyset$. By symmetric arguments, for each $j \in [m]$, T satisfies the non-clashing condition for $N[c'_j]$ and any other closed neighborhood in \mathcal{B} , as well as any pair of closed neighborhoods of clause vertices.

For all $i \in [n]$ and $j \in [m]$ such that $c_{j,i} \in T(N[c_j])$, $\tau(x_i)$ satisfies the clause C_j in φ , and thus, $T(N[v_i]) \cap N[c_j] = \emptyset$, resulting in $N[v_i]$ and $N[c_j]$ being distinguished by $T(N[v_i])$. For all $i \in [n]$ and $j \in [m]$ such that $c_{j,i} \notin T(N[c_j])$, $N[v_i]$ and $N[c_j]$ are distinguished by $T(N[c_j])$. The case analysis is complete, and so, T is a positive NCTM for \mathcal{B} .

Finally, note that both $|V(G)|$ and $|E(G)|$ are linear in the number of variables and clauses in the 3-SAT instance φ . So, if N-NCTD⁺ can be solved in $2^{o(f(k) \cdot (|V(G)| + |E(G)|))}$ time for a computable function f , then 3-SAT can be solved in $2^{o(n+m)}$ time as $f(k) = \mathcal{O}(1)$, contradicting the ETH. \square

Theorem 4. N-NCTD⁺ can be solved in $2^{\mathcal{O}(|E(G)|)}$ time.

Proof. For all $v \in V(G)$, $|N[v]| = d(v) + 1$, where $d(v)$ is the degree of v . Therefore, there are $2^{d(v)+1}$ choices for $T(N[v])$. So, there are at most $2^{\sum_{v \in V(G)} (d(v)+1)} = 2^{\mathcal{O}(|E(G)|)}$ distinct positive teaching maps for \mathcal{B} , each of which can be checked to be non-clashing or not in polynomial time. \square

3 Fixed-Parameter Algorithms

In this section, we prove that N-NCTD^+ is FPT parameterized by the *treedepth* of G and N-NCTD is FPT parameterized by the vertex cover number of G . As mentioned before, this further motivates considering closed neighborhoods instead of balls in graphs, as treedepth is a more general parameter than vertex integrity (see footnote 6), and no FPT algorithm was known when the teacher may use negatively-labeled examples. The *treedepth* $\text{td}(G)$ of a connected graph G is the minimum height of a rooted tree \mathcal{T} such that $V(\mathcal{T}) = V(G)$ and, for all $uv \in E(G)$, either u is an ancestor of v or v is an ancestor of u in \mathcal{T} . The tree \mathcal{T} is a *treedepth decomposition* of G (see Fig. 4 for an illustration).

Figure 4: (a) A graph G . (b) A treedepth decomposition \mathcal{T} of G witnessing $\text{td}(G) \leq 4$.

Theorem 5. N-NCTD^+ is FPT parameterized by the treedepth of G .

We prove Theorem 5 via an algorithm that exhaustively applies a reduction rule to prune the tree \mathcal{T} in the treedepth decomposition of G from the bottom up, yielding a tree whose number of vertices is a function of $\text{td}(G)$ (see Fig. 6). From there, we compute $\text{NCTD}^+(\mathcal{B})$ by brute force in FPT time w.r.t. $\text{td}(G)$. For simplicity, we state the reduction rule in more general terms and do not specify the component to delete. However, the proof that it is safe (Lemma 6) specifies the component; a reduction rule is *safe* if the input instance is a YES-instance if and only if the output instance is.

Reduction Rule 1. Let G be a graph, $X \subseteq V(G)$ a subset of its vertices, and $A = \{A_1, \dots, A_\ell\}$ a subset of the connected components of $G - X$ such that $\max_{i \in [\ell]} |A_i| = t$. If $\ell > (|X| + t) \cdot 2^{(|X|+t)^2} \cdot 2^{2t+|X|+1}$, then delete a particular connected component in A .

Lemma 6. Reduction rule 1 is safe for N-NCTD^+ .

Proof. First, we provide intuition. If ℓ is large, by the pigeonhole principle, there are 3 automorphic components in A that are “identical” with respect to their adjacencies in X , and the closed neighborhoods of \mathcal{B} that they contain along with their teaching sets. We select one of these 3 components, consider each teaching set that contains a vertex from it, and replace that vertex by one of its two automorphic copies (made possible by their identicalness), allowing that component to be deleted.

Formally, let $X \subseteq V(G)$ be such that $A = \{A_1, \dots, A_\ell\}$ is a subset of the connected components of $G - X$, where $\max_{i \in [\ell]} |A_i| = t$ and $\ell > (|X| + t) \cdot 2^{(|X|+t)^2} \cdot 2^{2t+|X|+1}$. Let T be a positive NCTM of size at most k for \mathcal{B} . We first prove that there exist $A_P, A_Q, A_R \in A$ that are automorphic to each other and such that, for any distinct $A_C, A_D \in \{A_P, A_Q, A_R\}$, there exists an automorphism $\sigma : V(A_C) \rightarrow V(A_D)$ where, for all $c \in V(A_C)$ and $d \in V(A_D)$ with $\sigma(c) = d$, it holds that:

1. $N(c) \cap X = N(d) \cap X$;
2. $N[c] \in \mathcal{B}$ if and only if $N[d] \in \mathcal{B}$;
3. if $N[c], N[d] \in \mathcal{B}$, then $T(N[c]) \cap X = T(N[d]) \cap X$ and, for all $u \in V(A_C)$ and $v \in V(A_D)$ with $\sigma(u) = v$, we have $u \in T(N[c]) \cap V(A_C)$ if and only if $v \in T(N[d]) \cap V(A_D)$.

We prove this via the pigeonhole principle. Trivially, the number of non-automorphic graphs on at most $|X| + t$ vertices is at most $(|X| + t) \cdot 2^{(|X|+t)^2}$. Thus, since $\ell > 2(|X| + t) \cdot 2^{(|X|+t)^2}$, there exist $A_P, A_Q, A_R \in \mathcal{A}$ that are automorphic to each other and such that, for any distinct $A_C, A_D \in \{A_P, A_Q, A_R\}$, there exists an automorphism $\sigma : V(A_C) \rightarrow V(A_D)$ where, for all $c \in V(A_C)$ and $d \in V(A_D)$ with $\sigma(c) = d$, 1. holds. Since $\ell > 2(|X| + t) \cdot 2^{(|X|+t)^2} \cdot 2^t$, we also have that 2. holds. Moreover, as $\ell > 2(|X| + t) \cdot 2^{(|X|+t)^2} \cdot 2^t \cdot 2^{t+|X|}$, we also have that 3. holds.

Select $w \in V(G) \setminus V(A_P)$ such that there exists $v \in T(N[w]) \cap V(A_P)$; we can assume w exists, as otherwise we delete $V(A_P)$. Note that $w \in X$. We show that removing v from $T(N[w])$ and adding a particular vertex $z \in V(A_Q) \cup V(A_R)$ to $T(N[w])$ maintains that T is a positive NCTM for \mathcal{B} in G . Let $\sigma_{P,Q} : V(A_P) \rightarrow V(A_Q)$ ($\sigma_{P,R} : V(A_P) \rightarrow V(A_R)$, resp.) be the automorphism between $V(A_P)$ and $V(A_Q)$ ($V(A_R)$, resp.). If $T(N[w]) \cap V(A_Q) = \emptyset$, then $z = \sigma_{P,Q}(v)$, and if not, but $\sigma_{P,R}(v) \notin T(N[w])$, then $z = \sigma_{P,R}(v)$, and otherwise no vertex is added to $T(N[w])$.

Let T' be the teaching map for \mathcal{B} obtained from T by applying the above procedure for all $w \in X$ and $v \in V(A_P)$ such that $v \in T(N[w])$. Note that T' has size at most k , and T' is a positive teaching map for \mathcal{B} since T is, and due to property 1. above. We show that T' is a positive NCTM for \mathcal{B} . Toward a contradiction, suppose there exist $x, y \in V(G)$ such that T' does not satisfy the non-clashing condition for $N[x]$ and $N[y]$. Due to how T' was obtained from T , and since T is an NCTM for \mathcal{B} , while T' is not, then the only vertices in $T(N[x]) \cup T(N[y])$ distinguishing $N[x]$ and $N[y]$ are in $V(A_P)$. Thus, w.l.o.g., $v \in (T(N[x]) \cup T(N[y])) \cap V(A_P)$ distinguished $N[x]$ and $N[y]$. Then, $\sigma_{P,Q}(v) \in T'(N[x]) \cup T'(N[y])$ and/or $\sigma_{P,R}(v) \in T'(N[x]) \cup T'(N[y])$, and, w.l.o.g., $v \in N[x]$ and $v \notin N[y]$. We do a case analysis (see Fig. 5). Let $u = \sigma_{P,Q}(v)$ and $u' = \sigma_{P,R}(v)$.

Case 1: $x \in N[v] \cap V(A_P)$. Thus, $v \in T'(N[x])$ distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[y]$, a contradiction.

Case 2: $x \in N(v) \cap X$ and $y \notin N[u]$. As $N(v) \cap X = N(u) \cap X = N(u') \cap X$, then $u, u' \in N[x]$. Hence, u', u or a vertex in $T'(N[x]) \cap V(A_Q)$ distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[y]$, a contradiction.

Case 3: $x \in N(v) \cap X$ and $y \in N[u]$. Thus, $y \in V(A_Q)$. Let $\sigma_{P,Q}(y') = y$. As T is an NCTM for \mathcal{B} , there exists $r \in T(N[x]) \cup T(N[y'])$ that distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[y']$. We now study subcases.

Case 3.1: $r \in T(N[y'])$. Here, $r \in T'(N[y])$ distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[y]$, a contradiction.

Case 3.2: $r \in T(N[x])$. If $r \notin V(A_P)$, then $r \in T'(N[x])$. If $r \in V(A_P)$, then $\sigma_{P,Q}(r) \in T'(N[x])$ and/or $\sigma_{P,R}(r) \in T'(N[x])$. We again study subcases.

Case 3.2.1: $r \notin N[y]$. If $r \notin V(A_P)$, then $r \in T'(N[x])$ distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[y]$, a contradiction. Otherwise, as $r \in T(N[x])$ distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[y']$, then $r \notin N[y']$, which implies that $\sigma_{P,Q}(r) \notin N[y]$. So, $\sigma_{P,Q}(r)$ or $\sigma_{P,R}(r)$ in $T'(N[x])$ distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[y]$, a contradiction.

Case 3.2.2: $r \in N[y]$. As T is an NCTM for \mathcal{B} , there exists $r' \in T(N[x]) \cup T(N[y])$ distinguishing $N[x]$ and $N[y]$. If $r' \in T(N[y])$, then $r' \in T'(N[y])$ distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[y]$. Hence, $r' \in T(N[x])$. Further, if $r' \notin N[y']$, then either $r' \notin V(A_P)$, and so, $r' \in T'(N[x])$, or $r' \in V(A_P)$, in which case $\sigma_{P,R}(r') \in T'(N[x])$ as $r \in T'(N[x]) \cap N[y]$. In both cases, T' satisfies the non-clashing condition for $N[x]$ and $N[y]$, a contradiction. Thus, $r' \in N[y']$, and as $r \in T'(N[x]) \cap N[y]$, then $\sigma_{P,R}(r') \in T'(N[x])$, which distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[y]$, a contradiction.

Figure 5: Cases 1, 2, and 3 in the forward direction of the proof of Lemma 6. Recall that $y \notin N[v]$.

That completes the case analysis, and thus, T' is a positive NCTM for \mathcal{B} . Let $G' := G - A_P$ and let \mathcal{B}' equal \mathcal{B} restricted to G' . Since the only teaching sets of T' containing vertices in $V(A_P)$ are those of the closed neighborhoods

centered in vertices of $V(A_P)$, then T' restricted to \mathcal{B}' is a positive NCTM of size at most k for \mathcal{B}' in G' . This completes the first direction of the proof.

For the reverse direction, we do the (simpler) inverse of the above. Let T' be a positive NCTM of size at most k for \mathcal{B}' in G' . Since there exists an automorphism $\sigma_{Q,R} : V(A_Q) \rightarrow V(A_R)$, then, for each $q \in V(A_Q)$ such that $N[q] \in \mathcal{B}'$, $T'(N[q]) \cap V(A_Q) \neq \emptyset$ and $T'(N[\sigma_{Q,R}(q)]) \cap V(A_R) \neq \emptyset$. Indeed, otherwise T' does not satisfy the non-clashing condition for that pair of closed neighborhoods. Note that the addition of $V(A_P)$ to G' does not make any two closed neighborhoods that were the same in G' become distinct in G . Hence, it is sufficient to extend T' to a positive NCTM T of size at most k for \mathcal{B} in G as follows. For all $p \in V(A_P)$, let $p' := \sigma_{P,Q}(p)$. For all $x \in V(G')$, set $T(N[x]) := T'(N[x])$, and, for all $p \in V(A_P)$ such that $N[p] \in \mathcal{B}$, set $T(N[p]) := (T(N[p']) \cap X) \cup_{q \in T(N[p']) \cap V(A_Q)} \{\sigma_{P,Q}^{-1}(q)\}$.

Note that T has size at most k and is a positive teaching map for \mathcal{B} . We now show that T is a positive NCTM for \mathcal{B} in G . Since $T(N[x]) := T'(N[x])$ for all $x \in V(G')$, we only need to show that T distinguishes $N[p]$ and $N[y]$ for all $p \in V(A_P)$ and $y \in V(G)$ such that $N[p], N[y] \in \mathcal{B}$. For all $p \in V(A_P)$, since $T(N[p]) \cap V(A_P) \neq \emptyset$, T satisfies the non-clashing condition for $N[p]$ and $N[y]$ for any $y \notin (V(A_P) \cup (N(p) \cap X))$. We now proceed with a case analysis.

Case 1: $y \in V(A_P) \setminus \{p\}$. Let $x \in T'(N[\sigma_{P,Q}(y)]) \cup T'(N[p'])$ distinguish $N[\sigma_{P,Q}(y)]$ and $N[p']$. If $x \in X$, then $x \in T(N[p]) \cup T(N[y])$ distinguishes $N[p]$ and $N[y]$. Otherwise, $x \in V(A_Q)$, and thus, $\sigma_{P,Q}^{-1}(x) \in T(N[p]) \cup T(N[y])$ distinguishes $N[p]$ and $N[y]$.

Case 2: $y \in N(p) \cap X$. If $x \in T'(N[p'])$ distinguishes $N[p']$ and $N[y]$, then either $x \in T(N[p]) \cap X$ or $x \in V(A_Q)$ and $\sigma_{P,Q}^{-1}(x) \in T(N[p])$. In both cases, T satisfies the non-clashing condition for $N[p]$ and $N[y]$. Otherwise, $x \in T'(N[y])$ distinguishes $N[p']$ and $N[y]$. Since $x \notin N[p']$ and $T'(N[y]) \cap V(A_P) = \emptyset$, then $x \notin N[p]$, and thus, $x \in T(N[y])$ distinguishes $N[p]$ and $N[y]$.

This completes the case analysis. Hence, T is a positive NCTM of size at most k for \mathcal{B} in G . \square

Proof of Theorem 5. Use the algorithm of [RRVS14] to compute a treedepth decomposition \mathcal{T} of G of depth $\text{td}(G)$ in $2^{\mathcal{O}(\text{td}(G)^2)} \cdot |V(G)|$ time. From the bottom of \mathcal{T} up, exhaustively apply Reduction rule 1, which is safe by Lemma 6. Specifically, first consider the children of a vertex at depth $\text{td}(G) - 1$. These children (leaves of \mathcal{T}) form A , and their ancestors in \mathcal{T} form X . Exhaustively apply Reduction Rule 1 for the children of each vertex at depth $\text{td}(G) - 1$. Once Reduction Rule 1 cannot be applied, each vertex at depth $\text{td}(G) - 1$ has at most $g_1(\text{td}(G))$ children, for a computable function g_1 . Proceeding by induction on the depth $\text{td}(G) - j$ of the considered vertices, suppose that, for some $1 \leq i < \text{td}(G)$, it holds that, for all $1 \leq j \leq i$, after exhaustively applying Reduction Rule 1, each vertex at depth $\text{td}(G) - j$ has at most $g_j(\text{td}(G))$ children for a computable function g_j . Then, exhaustively applying Reduction Rule 1 at depth $\text{td}(G) - i - 1$ results in each vertex at depth $\text{td}(G) - i - 1$ having at most $g_{i+1}(\text{td}(G))$ children for a computable function g_{i+1} . See Fig. 6 for an illustration of this pruning process. In total, exhaustively applying Reduction Rule 1 as above takes FPT time with respect to $\text{td}(G)$ as we need to find the components A_P , A_Q , and A_R each time. Once Reduction rule 1 cannot be applied at the root of \mathcal{T} , we have proven by induction that the remaining graph G' has at most $f(\text{td}(G))$ vertices, and thus, at most $f'(\text{td}(G))$ edges, for computable functions f and f' . Now, apply the algorithm of Theorem 4 on G' , which runs in $f''(\text{td}(G))$ time for a computable function f'' since $|E(G')| = f'(\text{td}(G))$. \square

Figure 6: Pruning of a treedepth decomposition as in the proof of Theorem 5.

We proceed with the vertex cover number parameterization for N-NCTD. The *vertex cover number* of a graph G is the minimum size of a subset of vertices $X \subseteq V(G)$ such that each edge in G is incident to at least one vertex in X . We emphasize that allowing negatively-labeled examples in the teaching sets poses a significant challenge as the problem is no longer local, which can be seen by comparing the proof of the next result with the one for STRICT NON-CLASH [CCMR24].

Theorem 7. N-NCTD is FPT parameterized by the vertex cover number of G .

We prove Theorem 7 via a kernelization algorithm⁷ which exhaustively applies two reduction rules. However, we first show that the solution size k can be bounded above by a function of the vertex cover number of G as this is a necessary condition for one of the reduction rules. To do so, we consider equivalence classes for the vertices in the independent set with respect to the vertex cover. Given a graph G , let $X \subseteq V(G)$ be a vertex cover of G , and $I := V(G) \setminus X$. Any two distinct vertices $u, v \in I$ are in the same *equivalence class* $\mathcal{S} \subseteq I$ if and only if u and v are false twins. Note that there are at most $2^{|X|}$ distinct equivalence classes for the vertices in I with respect to X .

Lemma 8. Given a graph G and a vertex cover $X \subseteq V(G)$ of G , for any \mathcal{B} consisting of closed neighborhoods of G , it holds that $\text{NCTD}(\mathcal{B}) \leq 2^{|X|+1} + |X|$.

Proof. It suffices to prove it for $\mathcal{B} = \{N[v] \mid v \in V(G)\}$ as the upper bound then holds for all $\mathcal{B}' \subseteq \mathcal{B}$. We construct an NCTM T of size at most $2^{|X|+1} + |X|$ for \mathcal{B} . Let $\mathcal{S}_1, \dots, \mathcal{S}_p$ be the distinct equivalence classes of size at least 1 of $I := V(G) \setminus X$ with respect to X . For each $x \in X$, set $T(N[x]) := X \cup \{s_1, \dots, s_p\} \cup \{t_1, \dots, t_p\}$, where s_i and t_i are any two distinct vertices in \mathcal{S}_i for all $i \in [p]$ (if $|\mathcal{S}_i| = 1$, then say that t_i does not exist). For each $y \in I$, set $T(N[y]) := X \cup \{y\}$. Since $p \leq 2^{|X|}$, T has size at most $2^{|X|+1} + |X|$. We now prove that T is an NCTM for \mathcal{B} . Consider the pair $N[u]$ and $N[v]$ for any two distinct vertices $u, v \in V(G)$. If $u, v \in I$, then T is non-clashing for $N[u]$ and $N[v]$ as $y \in T(N[y])$ for all $y \in I$. If $u \in X$ and $v \in I$, then T is non-clashing for $N[u]$ and $N[v]$ since if $N[u] \neq N[v]$, then either $v \in T(N[v])$ or some vertex in X distinguishes $N[u]$ and $N[v]$, or some vertex in $T(N[u]) \cap (I \setminus \{v\})$ distinguishes them. Lastly, if $u, v \in X$ and $N[u] \neq N[v]$, then some vertex in X is only in one of $N[u]$ and $N[v]$ and/or there exists an equivalence class \mathcal{S} of I such that all of \mathcal{S} is in $N[u]$ or $N[v]$ and none of \mathcal{S} is in the other. In the first case, T is non-clashing for $N[u]$ and $N[v]$ as $X \subseteq T(N[x])$ for all $x \in X$. In the second case, T is non-clashing for $N[u]$ and $N[v]$ as $\{s_1, \dots, s_p\} \subseteq T(N[x])$ for all $x \in X$. \square

Reduction Rule 2. Let G be a graph with a vertex cover $X \subseteq V(G)$ of G and let $q = 2^{2^{|X|+|X|}} + 1$. If $k < 2^{2^{|X|+1}} + |X|$ and there exist $q + 2k + 1$ vertices in $I := V(G) \setminus X$ that are pairwise false twins whose closed neighborhoods are in \mathcal{B} , then delete one of them.

Reduction Rule 3. Given a graph G and a vertex cover $X \subseteq V(G)$ of G , if there exists a pair $u, v \in V(G)$ of false twins in $I := V(G) \setminus X$ such that $N[u], N[v] \notin \mathcal{B}$, then delete v .

The next lemma is the key to proving Reduction rule 2 is safe. Roughly, it says that if there are too many false twins in I whose closed neighborhoods are in \mathcal{B} , then, by the pigeonhole principle, two of them will have almost “identical” teaching sets. This will facilitate the deletion of one of them.

Lemma 9. Let G be a graph with a vertex cover $X \subseteq V(G)$ of G , let u_1, \dots, u_ℓ be a set of pairwise false twins in the equivalence class Q of $I := V(G) \setminus X$ such that $N[u_1], \dots, N[u_\ell] \in \mathcal{B}$, let $k \leq 2^{2^{|X|+1}} + |X|$, and let $q = 2^{2^{|X|+|X|}} + 1$. For any NCTM T of size k for \mathcal{B} , if $\ell > q + 2k$, then there exist $i, j \in [\ell]$ such that $u_i \in T(N[u_i])$, $u_j \in T(N[u_j])$, $T(N[u_i]) \cap X = T(N[u_j]) \cap X$, $T(N[u_i]) \cap (Q \setminus \{u_i\}) = \emptyset$ if and only if $T(N[u_j]) \cap (Q \setminus \{u_j\}) = \emptyset$, and $T(N[u_i]) \cap \mathcal{S} = \emptyset$ if and only if $T(N[u_j]) \cap \mathcal{S} = \emptyset$ for any equivalence class $\mathcal{S} \neq Q$ of I with respect to X .

Proof. First, we prove that, for any NCTM T of size k for \mathcal{B} , if there exist q distinct indices $p \in [\ell]$ such that $u_p \in T(N[u_p])$, then there exist distinct $i, j \in [\ell]$ such that $u_i \in T(N[u_i])$, $u_j \in T(N[u_j])$, $T(N[u_i]) \cap X = T(N[u_j]) \cap X$, $T(N[u_i]) \cap (Q \setminus \{u_i\}) = \emptyset$ if and only if $T(N[u_j]) \cap (Q \setminus \{u_j\}) = \emptyset$, and $T(N[u_i]) \cap \mathcal{S} = \emptyset$ if

⁷A kernelization algorithm for a parameterized problem Π with input I and parameter p , runs in polynomial time and transforms an instance (I, p) of Π into an equivalent instance (I', p') of Π such that $|I'|, p' \leq f(p)$, for a computable function f . Π is FPT parameterized by p if and only if it admits a kernelization algorithm.

and only if $T(N[u_j]) \cap \mathcal{S} = \emptyset$ for any equivalence class $\mathcal{S} \neq Q$ of I with respect to X . So, assume that there exist q distinct indices $p \in [\ell]$ such that $u_p \in T(N[u_i])$. Since there are at most $2^{|X|}$ equivalence classes of I with respect to X , there are at most $2^{2^{|X|}}$ distinct subsets of these equivalence classes. Hence, there are at most $2^{2^{|X|}+|X|}$ distinct subsets of X and the equivalence classes. Thus, the existence of u_i and u_j with the above properties follows by the pigeonhole principle since $q = 2^{2^{|X|}+|X|} + 1 > 2^{2^{|X|}+|X|}$.

It remains to prove that, for any NCTM T of size k for \mathcal{B} , if $\ell > q + 2k$, then there exist q distinct indices $p \in [\ell]$ such that $u_p \in T(N[u_p])$. Toward a contradiction, let T be an NCTM of size k for \mathcal{B} , let $\ell > q + 2k$, and suppose there are at most $q - 1$ distinct indices $p \in [\ell]$ such that $u_p \in T(N[u_p])$. For all $i \in [\ell]$, if $u_i \notin T(N[u_i])$, then each of the at most k vertices in $T(N[u_i])$ distinguishes $N[u_i]$ and at most one other closed neighborhood in $\{N[u_1], \dots, N[u_\ell]\}$. Thus, w.l.o.g., for all $i \in [q - 1]$, let $u_i \in T(N[u_i])$. By the above analysis, the teaching sets of $N[u_q], \dots, N[u_\ell]$ combined distinguish at most $(\ell - q + 1)k$ pairs in $\{N[u_q], \dots, N[u_\ell]\}$. Note that $(\ell - q + 1)(\ell - q)/2$ such pairs must be distinguished and

$$(\ell - q + 1)(\ell - q)/2 > (\ell - q + 1)k \iff (\ell - q)/2 > k \iff \ell > q + 2k.$$

Thus, since $\ell > q + 2k$, T does not distinguish a pair in $\{N[u_q], \dots, N[u_\ell]\}$, a contradiction. \square

Lemma 10. *Reduction rule 2 is safe for N-NCTD.*

Proof. Let $Q \subseteq I$ be a set of $q + 2k + 1$ pairwise false twins, and let T be an NCTM of size at most k for \mathcal{B} . By Lemma 9, there exist $u, v \in Q$ such that $u \in T(N[u])$, $v \in T(N[v])$, $T(N[u]) \cap X = T(N[v]) \cap X$, $T(N[u]) \cap (Q \setminus \{u\}) = \emptyset$ if and only if $T(N[v]) \cap (Q \setminus \{v\}) = \emptyset$, and $T(N[u]) \cap \mathcal{S} = \emptyset$ if and only if $T(N[v]) \cap \mathcal{S} = \emptyset$ for any equivalence class $\mathcal{S} \neq Q$ of I with respect to X . Select any vertex $w \in V(G) \setminus \{v\}$ such that $v \in T(N[w])$. We show that removing v from $T(N[w])$ and adding $z \in Q$ to $T(N[w])$ maintains that T is an NCTM of size at most k for \mathcal{B} in G . Specifically, if $u \notin T(N[w])$, then $z = u$. Otherwise, z is any vertex in $Q \setminus \{u, v\}$ such that $z \notin T(N[w])$ (if $Q \setminus \{v\} \subseteq T(N[w])$, then no vertex is added to $T(N[w])$).

Let T' be the teaching map for \mathcal{B} obtained from T by applying the above procedure for all $w \in V(G) \setminus \{v\}$ such that $v \in T(N[w])$. Note that T' has size at most k . We show that T' is an NCTM for \mathcal{B} . Toward a contradiction, suppose there exist $x, y \in V(G)$ such that T' is not non-clashing for $N[x]$ and $N[y]$. Due to how T' was obtained, and as T is an NCTM for \mathcal{B} while T' is not, then v is the only vertex in $T(N[x]) \cup T(N[y])$ distinguishing $N[x]$ and $N[y]$. So, $u \in T'(N[x]) \cup T'(N[y])$ and, w.l.o.g., $v \in N[x]$ and $v \notin N[y]$. We do a case analysis (see Fig. 7).

Case 1: $x = v$. Here, $v \in T'(N[x])$ distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[y]$, a contradiction.

Case 2: $x \in N(v)$ and $y \neq u$. As $v \in N[x]$, $v \notin N[y]$, u and v are false twins, and $y \neq u$, then $u \in N[x]$ and $u \notin N[y]$. So, $u \in T'(N[x]) \cup T'(N[y])$ distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[y]$, a contradiction.

Case 3: $x \in N(v)$ and $y = u$. As in Case 2, it must be that $u \in N[x]$. Since $v \in N[x]$, there exists $r \in (T(N[x]) \cup T(N[v])) \setminus \{v\}$ that distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[v]$. We now study subcases.

Case 3.1: $r \in T(N[v]) \cap X$. Here, $r \in T'(N[u]) \cap X$ distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[u]$, a contradiction.

Case 3.2: $r \in T(N[v]) \cap \mathcal{S}$ for an equivalence class \mathcal{S} of I with respect to X . If $r = u$, then $\mathcal{S} = Q$ and there exists $z \in (T'(N[u]) \cap Q) \setminus \{u, v\}$ that distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[u]$, a contradiction. Otherwise, there is $r' \in (T'(N[u]) \cap \mathcal{S}) \setminus \{u, v\}$ that distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[u]$, a contradiction.

Case 3.3: $r \in T(N[x])$. In this case, $r \in T'(N[x])$. If $r \neq u$, then $r \in T'(N[x])$ distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[u]$, a contradiction. Otherwise, $r = u$. Since we have dealt with all the other cases, we can further assume that $r = u$ is the only vertex in $(T(N[x]) \cup T(N[v])) \setminus \{v\}$ that distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[v]$. Due to this property of r and the fact that T satisfies the non-clashing condition for $N[x]$ and $N[u]$, either $v \in T(N[x])$ or some vertex $r' \in T(N[u]) \setminus \{u\}$ distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[u]$. In the former case, as $u, v \in T(N[x])$, there exists $z \in (T'(N[x]) \cap Q) \setminus \{u, v\}$ that distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[u]$, a contradiction. In the latter case, if $r' \neq v$, then r' is also in $T'(N[u])$, and so, it distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[u]$, a contradiction. Otherwise, $r' = v$, and hence, there exists $z \in (T'(N[x]) \cap Q) \setminus \{u, v\}$ that distinguishes $N[x]$ and $N[u]$, a contradiction.

That completes the case analysis, and thus, T' is an NCTM for \mathcal{B} . Let $G' := G \setminus \{v\}$ and let \mathcal{B}' equal \mathcal{B} restricted to G' . Since the only teaching set of T' containing v is $T(N[v])$, then T' restricted to \mathcal{B}' is an NCTM of size at most k for \mathcal{B}' in G' . This completes the first direction of the proof.

Figure 7: Cases 1, 2, and 3 in the forward direction of the proof of Lemma 10. Recall that $y \notin N[v]$.

For the reverse direction, let T' be an NCTM of size at most k for \mathcal{B}' in G' . By Lemma 9, there exists $u \in V(G')$ such that $u \in T'(N[u])$ and u and v are false twins in G . Adding v to G' does not make any two closed neighborhoods that were the same in G' become distinct in G . Hence, it is sufficient to extend T' to an NCTM T of size at most k for \mathcal{B} in G as follows. Set $T(N[v]) := \{v\} \cup (T'(N[u]) \setminus \{u\})$, and, for all $x \in V(G')$, set $T(N[x]) := T'(N[x])$. Note that T has size at most k . We now show that T is an NCTM for \mathcal{B} in G . As $T(N[x]) := T'(N[x])$ for all $x \in V(G')$, we only need to show that T distinguishes $N[v]$ and $N[y]$ for all $y \in V(G) \setminus \{v\}$ such that $N[y] \in \mathcal{B}$. Since $v \in T(N[v])$, T satisfies the non-clashing condition for $N[v]$ and $N[y]$ for any $y \notin N[v]$. Otherwise, $y \in X \cap N(v)$. If $x \in T'(N[u])$ distinguishes $N[u]$ and $N[y]$, then $x \neq u$ since $u \in N[y]$ as u and v are false twins, and thus, x is also in $T(N[v])$ and distinguishes $N[v]$ and $N[y]$. Otherwise, $x \in T'(N[y])$ distinguishes $N[u]$ and $N[y]$, but $x \neq v$, and thus, $x \in T(N[y])$ also distinguishes $N[y]$ and $N[v]$. Hence, T is an NCTM of size at most k for \mathcal{B} in G . \square

Lemma 11. *Reduction rule 3 is safe for N-NCTD.*

Proof. Let T be an NCTM of size at most k for \mathcal{B} . For all $w \in V(G) \setminus \{v\}$ such that $v \in T(N[w])$, remove v from $T(N[w])$, and if $u \notin T(N[w])$, then add u to $T(N[w])$. From the proof that Reduction rule 2 is safe (Lemma 10), it is easy to see that this maintains that T is an NCTM of size at most k for \mathcal{B} since $N[u]$ and $N[v]$ are not in \mathcal{B} . The reverse direction is trivial since any NCTM for \mathcal{B}' in G' is also an NCTM for \mathcal{B} in G as $N[u]$ and $N[v]$ are not in \mathcal{B} . \square

Proof of Theorem 7. Compute a vertex cover $X \subseteq V(G)$ with the classic polynomial-time 2-approximation algorithm. By Lemma 8, if $k \geq 2^{|X|+1} + |X|$, then it is a YES-instance. Otherwise, exhaustively apply Reduction rules 2 and 3, which do not alter k and are safe by Lemmas 10 and 11. This is a kernelization algorithm: it takes polynomial time and the resultant graph has at most $2^{|X|}(q + 2k) + 2^{|X|} + |X| \leq 2^{|X|}(2^{2^{|X|}+1}|X| + 2^{|X|+2} + 2|X|) + |X|$ vertices. \square

4 Combinatorial Upper Bounds for Graph Classes

We finish by providing upper bounds on the (positive) non-clashing teaching dimension for closed neighborhoods \mathcal{B} of a graph G when G is restricted to planar or unit square graphs. Note that upper bounds for any \mathcal{B} hold for any $\mathcal{B}' \subseteq \mathcal{B}$, and $\text{VCD}(\mathcal{B}) \leq 4$ in both cases [DKP24].

Theorem 12. *For any planar graph G , if $\mathcal{B} = \{N[v] \mid v \in V(G)\}$, then $\text{NCTD}^+(\mathcal{B}) \leq 7$.*

Proof. We construct a positive NCTM T of size at most 7 for \mathcal{B} . For all $v \in V(G)$, if $d(v) \leq 6$, then set $T(N[v]) := N[v]$. Otherwise, for each $v \in V(G)$ with $d(v) \geq 7$, place any 3 neighbors of v in $T(N[v])$. Consider any one such vertex v and let v_1, v_2, v_3 be its 3 neighbors in $T(N[v])$. Since G is planar, there is at most one other vertex $u \in V(G)$ such that $v_1, v_2, v_3 \in N(u)$, as otherwise there would be a $K_{3,3}$. Hence, T satisfies the non-clashing condition for $N[v]$ and $N[x]$ for all $x \in V(G) \setminus \{v, u, v_1, v_2, v_3\}$ if u exists, and for all $x \in V(G) \setminus \{v, v_1, v_2, v_3\}$ otherwise.

As long as there exists a pair $N[v], N[y] \in \mathcal{B}$ such that $d(v) \geq 7$, $N[v] \neq N[y]$, and T does not currently satisfy the non-clashing condition for the pair, then there exists $w \in (N[v] \setminus N[y]) \cup (N[y] \setminus N[v])$ that will be added to $T(N[v])$ or $T(N[y])$ to distinguish the pair. Specifically, if $w \in N[v] \setminus N[y]$, then add w to $T(N[v])$, and otherwise, add $w \in N[y] \setminus N[v]$ to $T(N[y])$. In either case, T then satisfies the non-clashing condition for $N[v]$ and $N[y]$. Once this process is completed, T is a positive NCTM for \mathcal{B} as it is non-clashing for $N[v]$ and $N[y]$ for any vertex v with $d(v) \geq 7$, but also for the closed neighborhoods of any two vertices of degree at most 6 since their teaching sets coincide with their closed neighborhoods in this case. For each $v \in V(G)$ with $d(v) \geq 7$, as there were at most 4 possibilities for y (the vertices corresponding to $u, v_1, v_2,$ and v_3 above), then at most 4 vertices were added to any teaching set during this process. Thus, T has size at most 7. \square

Theorem 13. For any planar graph G , if $\mathcal{B} = \{N[v] \mid v \in V(G)\}$, then $NCTD(\mathcal{B}) \leq 5$.

Proof. We construct an NCTM T of size at most 5 for \mathcal{B} . For all $v \in V(G)$, if $d(v) \leq 4$, then set $T(N[v]) := N[v]$. Otherwise, for each $v \in V(G)$ with $d(v) \geq 5$, place any 3 neighbors of v in $T(N[v])$. Consider any one such vertex v and let v_1, v_2, v_3 be its 3 neighbors in $T(N[v])$. Then, as in the proof of Theorem 12, there is at most one other vertex $u \in V(G)$ such that $v_1, v_2, v_3 \in N(u)$, and hence, T satisfies the non-clashing condition for $N[v]$ and $N[x]$ for all $x \in V(G) \setminus \{v, u, v_1, v_2, v_3\}$ if u exists, and for all $x \in V(G) \setminus \{v, v_1, v_2, v_3\}$ otherwise. If $u \notin N[v]$, then add u to $T(N[v])$, and note that this ensures that T satisfies the non-clashing condition for $N[v]$ and $N[z]$ for all $z \in V(G) \setminus \{v\}$ since $u \notin N[v]$, but $u \in N[v_1]$, $u \in N[v_2]$, and $u \in N[v_3]$. Hence, in what follows, if u exists, then assume that $u \in N[v]$.

As long as there exists a pair $N[v], N[y] \in \mathcal{B}$ such that $d(v) \geq 5$, $N[v] \neq N[y]$, and T does not currently satisfy the non-clashing condition for the pair, then there exists $w \in (N[v] \setminus N[y]) \cup (N[y] \setminus N[v])$ that will be added to $T(N[v])$ or $T(N[y])$ to distinguish the pair. Specifically, if $w \in N[v] \setminus N[y]$, then add w to $T(N[v])$, and otherwise, add $w \in N[y] \setminus N[v]$ to $T(N[y])$. In either case, T then satisfies the non-clashing condition for $N[v]$ and $N[y]$. Once this process is completed, T is an NCTM for \mathcal{B} as it is non-clashing for $N[v]$ and $N[y]$ for any vertex v with $d(v) \geq 5$, but also for the closed neighborhoods of any two vertices of degree at most 4 since their teaching sets coincide with their closed neighborhoods in this case. We now argue that there were at most 2 possibilities for y above. The vertices in $\{u, v, v_1, v_2, v_3\}$ cannot form a K_5 since G is planar. Thus, one of the edges v_1v_2, v_1v_3 , and v_2v_3 is not in $E(G)$ since $uv \in E(G)$. Say, w.l.o.g., that $v_2v_3 \notin E(G)$. Then, y could only have been u or v_1 . Hence, at most 2 vertices were added to any teaching set during the above process, and thus, T has size at most 5. \square

We end with *unit square graphs*: the intersection graphs of axis-parallel unit squares in the plane.

Theorem 14. For any unit square graph G , if $\mathcal{B} = \{N[v] \mid v \in V(G)\}$, then $NCTD^+(\mathcal{B}) \leq 4$.

Proof. We construct a positive NCTM T of size at most 4 for \mathcal{B} . For all $v \in V(G)$, let $R(v)$ be the minimum rectangle enclosing $N[v]$ in the plane (see Fig. 8). If a square u does not intersect v , then for one of the directions left, right, up, or down, u is farther in that direction than a square contained in $R(v)$ that is the farthest in that direction. Thus, u is not contained in $R(v)$, and each square in $R(v)$ intersects v . For all $v \in V(G)$, $T(N[v])$ consists of the vertices represented by the leftmost, rightmost, topmost, and bottommost squares in $R(v)$ (they may not be unique). Consider any $u \in V(G) \setminus \{v\}$. If $R(u) \neq R(v)$, then there exists $x \in T(N[u]) \cup T(N[v])$ that distinguishes $N[u]$ and $N[v]$. Indeed, w.l.o.g., say that part of $R(u)$ is farther to the left than all of $R(v)$; then, $x \in T(N[u])$ is the leftmost square in $R(u)$, and $x \notin N[v]$ as part of $R(u)$ is farther to the left than all of $R(v)$. If $R(u) = R(v)$, then $N[u] = N[v]$ as each square in $R(v)$ ($R(u)$, resp.) intersects v (u , resp.). \square

Figure 8: In the proof of Theorem 14, the minimum rectangles $R(u)$ (blue) and $R(v)$ (red) enclosing $N[u]$ and $N[v]$, respectively. The leftmost square in $R(u)$ ($u_1 \in T(N[u])$) is not contained in $R(v)$.

5 Conclusion

We studied non-clashing teaching for closed neighborhoods in graphs, notably providing highly non-trivial FPT algorithms and strong algorithmic lower bounds. Several open directions remain for future work, such as exploring the complexity with respect to treewidth or planarity for $N\text{-NCTD}^+$ and $N\text{-NCTD}$, as well as vertex integrity and treedepth for $N\text{-NCTD}$. However, like NON-CLASH [GKMR25], we expect that they are $W[1]$ -hard parameterized by the treewidth. It is also important to determine whether Theorem 13 is tight, since the balls of a planar graph has been mentioned [CCMR24] as a potential concept class \mathcal{C} negatively answering the question of [KSZ19, FKS⁺23], i.e., such that $\text{NCTD}(\mathcal{C}) > \text{VCD}(\mathcal{C})$.

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